

TOOL SHARPENING DEVICE FOR LATHE CUTTERS AND CARBIDE INSERTS

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ABSTRACT: *The demands of modern machining technologies necessitate the design of cutting tools with precise geometric parameters, ensuring optimal functional performance for efficient cutting. Both tool manufacturing and subsequent re-sharpening processes require thorough analysis to preserve the original geometric profile, especially for tools with defined contours used in copy cutting methods. The objective of this study is to enhance cutting tool performance by developing sharpening solutions that maintain stable geometry and surface roughness within the specifications outlined in technical documentation. The proposed device minimizes vibration through strategic design of its moving components, offering a cost-effective solution. Sharpening is conducted using a standard RP 250 grinding machine, as opposed to a universal sharpening machine, which incurs higher costs. Additionally, the device is compact, lightweight, and facilitates quick, convenient, and safe adjustment operations during sharpening.*

KEYWORDS: *device, defined profile, lathe tool, removable insert, angle, copying method*

1 INTRODUCTION

In metal cutting operations, the geometry and quality of cutting tools play a crucial role. The geometry of cutting tools is designed and finalized on specialized machinery, tailored to the specific operation to be performed. It is well-established that sometimes customized tools and inserts are required for various machining methods, such as copy cutting, which demands specific profiles. Tool and insert manufacturers typically produce them only for standard profiles, which are not always suitable for the mentioned machining methods. For example, when cutting a trapezoidal thread, the profile angle needs to be 30°, whereas for thread milling, the profile angle must be 40°. These specific geometries are achieved using the device presented in our research, which sharpens removable inserts at angles of 35° and 55° to the required angles. After sharpening, the inserts undergo a coating process with hard carbide layers to restore their strength and durability. It is important to note that these modified inserts can be reused, leading to cost savings by reintroducing them into the production cycle. The idea for this study emerged from an observation made in workshop practice.

The main motivation behind this work was the recovery of worn removable inserts for several reasons. One primary reason was to optimize the

cutting process by improving the geometry of the inserts, adapting the cutting edge angles to meet the requirements of a high-performance cutting operation.

Another important consideration was the safety and durability of the insert during operation. This is particularly relevant as tools with inserts fixed by hard soldering can sometimes be brittle and break during cutting, compromising the workpiece being processed. In addition, a key advantage of this method is that the sharpening direction is aligned along the cutting edge, unlike other methods using diamond disc grinding, which can introduce undesirable surface roughness to the cutting edges of the inserts. This roughness, in turn, negatively affects the quality of the surfaces being machined.

The goal of scientific research is to discover the laws that govern natural phenomena, with the aim of applying them for the benefit of mankind. To achieve this, it is essential to combine scientific study and research with practical technical applications, as any abstract speculation becomes sterile in comparison. In order to realize this objective, the first condition is to analyze and identify the problem to be solved, the approach to be taken, and the means of implementation, including cost-benefit analysis. Like any new development, it must bring added value, both through enhanced performance and reduced

manufacturing costs. This device fulfills these requirements through competitive design, simple and reliable construction, stability in use, and the use of common materials without special structural or compositional demands. This design is justified by both technical and economic performance considerations, particularly through the reintroduction of worn removable inserts into the productive cycle.

2. THE DEVICE

Fig. 1 Overview

The device consists of a main frame support (1) that holds the auxiliary elements of the construction (Fig. 1). An inclined lower support (2) (base support) is mounted on it, with an 8° inclination. The 8° angle was chosen because it corresponds to the setting angle α , as described in the specialized literature ($4^\circ \dots 8^\circ$). At the top, there is an oscillating arm (3) that moves left to right, which houses the insert guide and fixation support (4). Additionally, knives can also be fixed there for sharpening purposes. On the front of the main support, there are reference marks representing the semi-angle value at the tip of the tool, $\epsilon/2$. Similarly, the movable insert fixation support has a ridge to orient the insert to a specific angular value. This device can be used to sharpen inserts and tools intended for generating trapezoidal threads at 30° , saw-tooth profiles at 33° , cylindrical worms at 40° , metric threads at 60° , and Whitworth threads at 55° (in inches). The types of

inserts that can be sharpened are rhombic at 35° and 55° , which do not require a special fixation configuration, a consideration that was taken into account during the design of this device. The consistency and safety of insert fixation during the entire sharpening process are ensured by a central screw that provides firm attachment. After sharpening, the inserts undergo a coating process with metal carbides to restore their original performance regarding hardness and durability required for cutting. The sharpening process is completed after two left-right fixation cycles in the insert holder. To perform sharpening, the presented device is placed on the magnetic table of an RP 250 grinding machine, with a diamond disc mounted on the main shaft for the subsequent sharpening operation.

3. OPERATION OF THE DEVICE

After securing the device on the table of the surface grinding machine RP250, which is equipped with a diamond wheel, the actual sharpening process takes place in the following steps:

Step 1. The replaceable insert to be sharpened is mounted in the insert holder (4) using the central screw. Next, the movable support (3) is positioned so that the reference mark on it aligns with the desired sharpening half-angle value $\epsilon/2$, on the left side, and is then locked in place (Fig. 2). In the following stage, the sharpening of the first surface—located in the seating plane (left side)—is performed using the diamond grinding wheel.

Fig. 2 – Step 1: The replaceable insert is mounted in the insert holder

Step 2. Next, the movable support (3) is released and repositioned to the adjacent angle, aligning the reference mark on it with the desired sharpening half-angle value $\epsilon/2$ on the right side, then locked in place (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Step 2: releasing the movable support (3) and moving it to the adjacent angle position

In the following stage, as in Step 1, the sharpening of the second surface—located in the seating plane (right side)—is performed using the diamond grinding wheel. It is important to note that, in order to ensure the symmetry of the insert's profile and the tool tip angle ϵ , it is necessary to maintain the same depth of cut into the insert for both steps. It can be observed that the cutting direction of the diamond wheel is parallel to the cutting edge of the insert formed during sharpening. This provides a scraping effect during chip removal, particularly in oblique cutting, which has a positive impact on both the cutting process and the quality of the machined surfaces. After completing the two steps described above, the insert is removed from its holder, rotated 180° around the central hole, and fixed again in the working position using the locking screw. The previous steps are then repeated for the other two lateral surfaces, resulting in a total of four cutting edges.

For the sharpening of lathe tools, the procedure is simpler. The tool is mounted on the movable support (3), with the front face facing the device and the tip oriented to the left. The support is then

moved to the left until the reference mark aligns with the desired tip half-angle value $\epsilon/2$, and is locked in this position. Subsequently, the left-side surface is ground (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 – Grinding of the left flank

Next, the movable support (3) is unlocked and moved to the right, with the tool tip oriented to the right, aligning the reference mark with the tip half-angle value $\epsilon/2$. The support is then locked in this position, and the second lateral seating surface on the right side is ground (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 – Grinding of the right flank

It should be noted that, as in the case of sharpening hard inserts, it is necessary to maintain the same depth of cut for both the left and right seating surfaces, in order to ensure symmetry of the tool profile with respect to its central axis. After completing this operation cycle for both inserts and tools, the tip width “b” is obtained, corresponding to the calculated value required for trapezoidal threads and worms.

4. RESULTS

When sharpening the insert using the peripheral part of the diamond wheel, the quality and geometry of the resulting cutting edges on the inserts are not compromised, unlike other methods where cutting takes place with the front face of the cup-shaped diamond wheel, which imparts a fan effect with a serrated cutting edge. This, in turn, produces a rough surface on the flanks of the thread formed with these inserts. Through competitive design, the number of components has been reduced, providing the device with greater rigidity. The symmetry and angular accuracy of the cutting edges are ensured and guaranteed according to the values specified in the technical documentation. This device can be attributed characteristics such as accuracy, reliability, and fidelity—traits typical of measuring and technical control instruments. By orienting the cutting trajectory along the cutting edge of the insert, the surface quality from which the cutting edges result is improved, achieving surface roughness values of $R_a = 0.069 \dots 0.104 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Measurement of the surface roughness of the machined surface

The copy-turning method of cutting causes the surface roughness of the cutting tool to be directly transferred to the machined surfaces, thereby guaranteeing the surface quality achieved through this process. Additionally, the device weighs only approximately 400 grams, making it easy to handle.

The novelty of this device lies in the positioning method of the insert during sharpening and the accuracy of the machining process. No negative results have been reported, as the system has been physically built and tested in the mechanical workshop through dimensional measurements of precisely executed angular values and flank profiles, with results falling within the acceptable tolerance limits.

This product has been practically finalized in the mechanical workshop, and the proposed solutions can be validated. Using this device, geometries of indexable inserts were produced, which were then used to manufacture entire batches of parts for demanding and certified customers who have recognized and appreciated the device.

5. CONCLUSIONS

By introducing this device, the sharpening process gains a high degree of precision, safety, and ease of handling. Through the application of competitive design principles, the number of components in the device was reduced without compromising its performance. This model demonstrates a high level of reliability and offers a wide range of possibilities for shaping various profiles. The active components responsible for the device's functionality—namely the insert holder support and the base plate—are designed to provide both rigidity and stability in the working position, while also ensuring the necessary flexibility for handling. This version of the device can serve as a starting point for further research and development in this field. The construction of this simple, yet reliable and high-performance device can be achieved using standard technical resources and minimal cost, without requiring machining on universal sharpening machines.

6. REFERENCES

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